

D1.2 – Living Lab Methodology

WP1 – Task 1.5

28 February 2025 (M2)

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Document information

Describe here shortly the content of this document (2 lines maximum).

Grant Agreement	101178306
Project Title	INNOVADE—INNOVative DEmocracy through digitalisation
Related Work Package	Work Package 1
Related Task(s)	Task 1.5
Lead Organisation	Beyond the Horizon ISSG
Contributing Partner(s)	
Due Date	28/02/2025
Submission Date	28/02/2025
Dissemination level	Public
Licence of the document	CC-BY

Document History

Date	Version	Edited by	Description
09/01/2025	0.1	Fatih Yilmaz	Presented at the kick-off meeting
22/01/2025	0.2	Pierre Roberts	Comments, inputs of the 1 st Living Lab added into the document
25/02/2025	0.3	Fatih Yilmaz	Comments, inputs incorporated into the document
09/02/2025	0.3	Pierre Roberts	Theoretical framework and developed methodology included
18/02/2025	0.4	Fatih Yilmaz	Methodology proofing with Elisabeth Calderon Luning (KT4D) and Berta Mizsei (Democratic Odyssey)
23/02/2025	1.0	Fatih Yilmaz	Practical examples and techniques added into the document
03/03/2025	1.1	Laurien Coenen	Reviewed by KUL
03/03/2025	1.2	Christian Fuchs	Reviewed by UPB
10/03/2025	1.3	Pierre Roberts	Review results incorporated
28/03/2025	1.4	Fatih Yilmaz	Final version

Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbr.	Description	Abbr.	Description
WP	Work Package	IT	Information Technologies
LL	Living Lab	AI	Artificial Intelligence

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Executive Summary

This document outlines the Living Lab methodology for the INNOVADE project, ensuring a coordinated and coherent approach across all Living Labs and the project's three-year duration. The methodology is designed to facilitate collaboration among stakeholders from diverse sectors, fostering co-creation in digital democracy initiatives. As Living Labs are central to INNOVADE's interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary exchange, this document also compiles a project-level glossary of agreed terms to standardise references across the consortium.

The document's first chapter consists of a theoretical background, distinguishing between co-design, co-production, and co-creation, with co-creation identified as the most suitable framework for INNOVADE's Living Labs. Key characteristics, challenges, and best practices for overcoming obstacles in co-creation are examined, followed by a definition of Living Labs and their essential components. Three case studies (KT4D, Democratic Odyssey, and SPRING) illustrate successful applications of co-creation principles in similar initiatives.

Chapter 2 then presents a structured methodology, which is divided into five phases: Understand, Frame, Ideate, Evaluate, and Test. Each phase employs specific techniques to engage stakeholders, generate insights, and iteratively refine solutions. The document further details the implementation framework for Living Labs in chapter 3, structured into four stages: Planning and Preparation, User-Centric Design and Co-Creation, Iterative Implementation, and Analysis and Reporting. Lessons from the first Living Lab (LL1) are incorporated to refine these steps, ensuring a methodology that is responsive to the perspectives of citizens and public sector agencies.

The final chapter presents the implementation plan for INNOVADE's seven Living Labs, each addressing different aspects of digital democracy. The methodology supports inclusive and participatory processes, leveraging diverse expertise to develop practical tools and a digital democracy application.

This document provides a robust framework for implementing Living Labs within the INNOVADE project, ensuring structured, iterative, and stakeholder-driven innovation. By employing co-creation as the guiding methodology, Living Labs will generate meaningful insights and tangible outcomes that enhance digital democracy. The structured approach, informed by theoretical foundations and real-world applications, ensures that the methodology is adaptable and scalable.

Key next steps include the implementation of upcoming Living Labs (LL2 to LL7), each addressing specific themes related to digital democracy. This methodology is not written on stone and can be refined by continuous iteration based on insights gathered from each Living Lab to enhance effectiveness. The findings and results of each LL will be compiled into reports, will be added into this document as new chapters. These will include inputs to policy recommendations, and practical tools to support digital governance.

Living Labs methodology will, in an iterative approach, contribute to the development of the Digital Democracy Application based on inputs from stakeholders, ensuring an inclusive and user-centric design.

By following this structured methodology, INNOVADE's Living Labs will serve as a dynamic environment for innovation, ensuring that digital democracy initiatives are practical, scalable, and aligned with the needs of all stakeholders involved.

INNOVADE Living Lab Methodology

1 Background

1.1 Co-creation of public services

Co-creation as a driving method

Due to the user-centric aspect of INNOVADE's Living Labs, it is important to understand the notion of co-creation. Co-creation is generally defined as the involvement of service-using citizens in contributing to the improvement of public services (Verschuere, Brandsen, & Pestoff 2012; Van Eijk, & Steen, T. 2014). More specifically, co-creation is centred on problem-solving, often in social or local contexts, with an emphasis on creativity and idea generation (Lee, Feiertag, and Unger 2024). Co-creation involves a process where public and private actors pool their knowledge, experiences, resources, skills, and ideas to address a common challenge, problem, or task, fostering the creation of public value and improving service delivery (Torfing 2019). It is important to note that co-creation can also involve a range of third-party actors who may not be direct users (such as companies, academic experts, field specialists, and civil society organisations), but can still contribute valuable knowledge and insights (Rubio et al. 2020). Through its broader emphasis on promoting engagement in the phase of project management and delivery with the participation of various stakeholders having shared responsibility (Lee, Feiertag, and Unger 2024), we decided that co-creation concept is best suited to INNOVADE's Living Labs.

The roles of stakeholders in co-creation

Central to the concept of co-creation is that of the service user as that of a client. In the private sector context, co-creation processes depend on the active participation of clients, who may either assume specific roles within the production chain or contribute their expertise through personal experiences and recommendations; in the context of the public sector however, this role is fulfilled by the citizen (Voorberg, Bekkers & Tummers (2015). This process doesn't happen in a two-way manner where the organisation is the service provider, and the citizen is the service user and the client; instead, it relies on the client to add value to the service through their inputs (Alford 1998).

When addressing the type of citizen involved in co-creation, several typologies appear. Voorberg, Bekkers & Tummers (2015) define three broad types of citizen and their involvement in co-creation: the citizen as a co-implementer, where the citizen only performs some implementation tasks; the citizen as a co-designer, where the citizen decides how the service delivery initiated by the public service organisation is designed; and the citizen as an initiator, where the citizen initiates and the public service follows it up. Adding to this, Van Eijk and Steen (2014) define four more specific types of citizen co-producers, namely: the semi-professionals, whose co-creation hinges on the strong focus on the improving of public service efficiency and effectiveness; the socialisers, who seek to foster trust and open communication between service providers and users as a way to stay connected to their community rather than to drive change; the network professionals, who believe in making a tangible impact to collective wellbeing through structured efforts by working within the system through

volunteering or nonprofits; and the aware co-producers, who focus on ethical and structured interventions that represent broader community needs to create meaningful, well-planned service improvements.

When defining the involvement of client/stakeholders in co-creation, we can refer to Bovaird (2007), who defines seven different models based on the level of involvement from professionals, users, and communities. While they are defined in the context of co-production, the way by which they are defined still make them relevant to the concept of co-creation and an umbrella concept that we have decided to use within this project:

1. Traditional professional service provision with user–community consultation, where professionals deliver services, but users and communities are consulted during planning and design;
2. User codelivery of professionally designed services, where professionals plan and design services, while users and communities take part in delivering them;
3. Full user–professional co-production, where users and professionals share planning, design, and service delivery equally;
4. User–community codelivery without formal planning, where users and community groups provide services independently but seek professional help when needed;
5. User–community sole delivery of professionally planned services, where community members take full responsibility for delivering services designed by professionals;
6. User–community sole delivery of co-planned or co-designed services, where users and community members design and deliver services themselves;
7. Traditional self-organised community provision, where community members provide services independently, without professional involvement.

To add to this, we can refer to the BecoDigital project, jointly organised by KU Leuven, the University of Namur, the University of Antwerp, and Sciensano, which seeks to create a practical, research-based roadmap to help governments effectively engage citizens in co-creating public services using digital technologies. Referring to its Baseline Measurement (Coenen et al. 2023), it is highlighted that stakeholders can take various roles when undertaking co-creation, depending on who is involved, when they participate, how deeply they engage, and why they take part. Quoting Linders (2012) and Bovaird and Loeffler (2013), public actors and citizens' roles are distinguished, but the authors explicitly outline that these roles are not limited to citizens and government actors as other external stakeholders may also take on similar responsibilities. With regard to public actors, the authors highlight that they can take on the role of framers (where they set participation rules to ensure fairness and inclusivity), sponsors (where they provide financial or other resources to support the initiative), mobilisers (where they encourage and sustain citizen involvement), monitors (where they oversee the process and outcomes, maintaining accountability) and providers of last resort (where they step in if solutions fail to emerge). Citizens are also shown to play multiple roles in co-creation, such as that of strategic thinkers and funders (where they share their needs and expectations), innovators (where they offer unique insights particularly on complex societal issues), asset-holders (where they contribute skills, time, and resources to improve services), legitimators/testimonial providers (where they advocate for the value of public services), co-

workers/financiers (where they encourage others to participate and support funding efforts), and evaluators (where they assess whether policies and services meet their needs and suggest improvements).

Challenges of co-creation

The challenge when applying co-creation isn't tailoring the product to the client but is rather finding a way to motivate the client to contribute to the project in a meaningful way. (Alford 1998). Citizens require greater motivation when participation involves significant hurdles or demands considerable effort in engaging with public policies, services, and regulations that address urgent societal issues; in such cases, the topics must be relevant or relatable to the participants. (Verschuere, Brandsen, & Pestoff 2012). In cases where citizens relate to the situation at hand, other hurdles present themselves in the form of complex and inaccessible policy details, information overflow, and digitally inaccessible tools that alienate citizens from co-creating due to their jargon-filled nature (Voorberg, Bekkers & Tummers 2015). If participating presents itself as too difficult, less people will involve themselves or will do so in less regular and organised ways, even if the topic is particularly relevant to them (Verschuere, Brandsen, & Pestoff 2012).

Additionally, resistance to co-creation techniques often appear in its initial stages, particularly from more powerful spheres which fear that increased involvement of clients could lead to a loss of influence or power on their part (Bovaird 2007). By treating members of the public as clients in the context of public service provision, it appears to better elicit their willingness to comply and contribute by co-creating (Alford 1998). While wealthier community members tend to hold more resources, studies show that public service participation often engages less affluent individuals; this has led to a debate on whether marginalised communities should be expected to participate to ensure service quality, with some arguing that these communities should not need to participate to access basic services, and others highlighting that involvement in co-creation can empower people (especially in deprived areas) helping them feel more in control (Bovaird 2007).

Overcoming challenges to co-creation

Co-creation is most effective when its common resources are properly pooled, and is best enacted when several factors align, namely: clear local boundaries, adaptation of rules to local circumstances, citizen involvement in decision-making, a restraint from authorities in organising communities, and supportive social infrastructure that can assist stakeholders in situations of conflict (Verschuere, Brandsen, & Pestoff 2012). This can be linked to what Van Eijk and Steen (2014) highlight as the four main factors that motivate citizens to co-produce, which are community-centred motivations, self-centred motivations, human and social capital, and internal efficacy. Empowerment and motivation of communities and citizens in co-producing comes from relevant social, economic or political issues and the importance citizens attach to them, as well as trust in public services and confidence in their own ability (Bovaird 2007; Van Eijk & Steen 2014). Depending on costs and efficiency concerns, professionals may prefer direct user involvement in service delivery but may rely on community representatives for planning and management (Bovaird 2007). Effective co-creation is put into place by balancing intra-organisational conditions (combining addressing the clients' needs with what

the organisation requires from the client within the context) and including relevant types of organisations in relation to co-creation (non-profit organisations tend to be more conducive to co-creation than for-profit or public sector organisations) (Verschuere, Brandsen, & Pestoff 2012).

Digital co-creation of (e-)services

A final note of interest to make in the context of this theoretical background is that of digital co-creation of (e-)services. Here, we once again referring to Coenen et al. (2023) and the BecoDigital project, which outlines that this kind of co-creation involves collaborative efforts using digital tools or other means to develop and improve public solutions, policy, services and regulations. For this kind of co-creation to be effective, the authors highlight the necessity of engagement from multiple stakeholders, including public and private actors, who work together to design, implement, and evaluate digital services. This process requires clear objectives, inclusive participation, and the strategic use of technology, and while some initiatives focus solely on internal government efficiencies, meaningful co-creation in this domain prioritises active citizen involvement to ensure public solutions, policy, services and regulations align with public needs. In order to enhance digital public service and deliver said e-services, one must properly understand the dynamics at play during the process of co-creation.

1.2 Living labs as a method of co-creation

A living lab is an open innovation ecosystem in real-life settings, where user-driven innovation is facilitated through collaboration among public-private-people partnerships. Chesbrough and Bogers (2014) define open innovation as a process that involves the goal-directed management of knowledge flows across organisational boundaries. The Living Lab approach leverages both external and internal knowledge sources to accelerate innovation and expand opportunities. It is used to co-design, co-create, and/or co-produce a prototype, then to validate and test these new services, products, and systems in real-world environments. Schuurman et al. (2025) credit the development of the first living labs to Professor William Mitchell, who envisioned experimental environments where volunteers lived temporarily, allowing researchers to observe and refine new home technologies.

The idea of integrating innovations into daily life laid the groundwork for what would become Living Labs, a movement which gained momentum in Europe through the influence of earlier initiatives such as the Scandinavian Participatory Design Movement of the 1960s and 1970s. In the 1980s, European social experiments explored how information technologies could benefit society, reinforcing the idea that technology should serve collective interests. The 1990s saw the rise of Digital City Projects, which focused on building digital infrastructure and fostering multi-stakeholder collaborations. These projects, though sometimes criticised for being overly technology-driven, highlighted the potential of technology to enhance urban life. By the early 2000s, Living Labs began to emerge in Europe, with cities like Barcelona and Helsinki leading the way.

1.3 Key Characteristics and Components

Here are key characteristics and components of living labs:

- **Real-Life Environments:** Living labs operate in everyday settings rather than controlled environments, ensuring that innovations are tested and developed under realistic conditions.
- **User-Centric:** Users are actively involved in the innovation process, contributing ideas, feedback, and participation in testing and development. This helps ensure that the innovations meet actual needs and preferences.
- **Co-Creation:** Multiple stakeholders, including citizens, researchers, companies, and public authorities, collaborate throughout the innovation process. This multidisciplinary approach leverages diverse perspectives and expertise.
- **Public-Private-People Partnerships (4Ps):** Successful living labs often involve collaboration between the public sector (governments and municipalities), private sector (businesses and industries), academia (universities and research institutions), and citizens.
- **Iterative Process:** Living labs follow an iterative approach where solutions are continuously developed, tested, and refined based on user feedback and real-world performance.
- **Sustainability and Scalability:** Innovations developed in living labs aim to be sustainable and scalable, addressing broader societal challenges and creating long-term value.

Examples of living labs can include:

- **Smart Cities:** Urban areas where technology and data are used to improve infrastructure, transportation, energy management, and public services.
- **Healthcare:** Environments where new medical technologies, treatments, and healthcare services are tested with patient involvement.
- **Sustainable Living:** Communities focused on testing and implementing sustainable practices and technologies in housing, energy use, and waste management.

Living labs provide a practical and dynamic approach to innovation, ensuring that new solutions are not only technically feasible but also socially acceptable and economically viable.

1.4 General Guidelines for Living Labs

The optimum time requirement to conduct a living lab can vary significantly depending on several factors, including the nature of the project, the complexity of the innovation, the stakeholders involved, and the specific goals of the living lab. However, some general guidelines can be considered:

- **Project Scope and Complexity:** Simpler projects may require shorter time frames, ranging from a few months to a year. More complex or large-scale projects, such as urban development or healthcare system innovations, may span several years.
- **Iterative Development:** Living labs follow an iterative process, where feedback loops and multiple testing phases are crucial. Each iteration might take a few weeks to several months. It's essential to allow enough time for multiple iterations to refine and improve the solution.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Time is needed to ensure meaningful involvement of all stakeholders, including users, researchers, businesses, and public authorities. Building

trust and effective communication among participants can require significant time upfront.

- **Real-World Testing:** Since living labs operate in real-life environments, the testing phases should be long enough to capture a wide range of data and user experiences. This might mean accounting for seasonal variations, usage patterns, and unforeseen challenges.
- **Evaluation and Scaling:** After initial testing and refinement, additional time is often needed for comprehensive evaluation, impact assessment, and scaling of successful innovations.
- **Regulatory and Ethical Considerations:** Especially in fields like healthcare, adhering to regulatory requirements and ethical considerations can add time to the living lab process.

Examples of Time Frames

- **Short-Term Projects:** Pilot projects or initial feasibility studies might last from 6 months to 1 year.
- **Medium-Term Projects:** Projects with moderate complexity, such as new public services or community initiatives, could take 1 to 2 years.
- **Long-Term Projects:** Large-scale or highly complex projects, such as smart city initiatives or systemic healthcare changes, may span 3 to 5 years or more.

It is important to maintain a balance between having a structured timeline and being flexible to adapt to emerging insights and challenges. Regular checkpoints, clear milestones, and adaptive planning can help manage the process effectively.

In summary, while there is no one-size-fits-all answer to the optimum time requirement for conducting living labs, considering the factors mentioned above and tailoring the timeline to the specific project's needs will help ensure successful outcomes.

1.5 Practical examples of co-creation in action

To better illustrate the concepts highlighted above, we have selected three projects that used these concepts in their own methodology to further their results. These projects are Knowledge Technologies for Democracy (KT4D), Democratic Odyssey, and the Sustainable PRactices of INteGration (SPRING) project.

Knowledge Technologies for Democracy (KT4D) integrates a user-centric approach framed around the concepts of identity and culture to investigate and bring to light the ways by which rapidly developing technologies such as AI and big data can be used in a beneficial manner by its users. KT4D operates in a similar manner to INNOVADE, embedding co-creation within its framework by integrating stakeholder contributions across a variety of tasks. It uses a system of 'user cases' that function much like INNOVADE's Living Labs, where stakeholders participate in initial workshops, digital democracy labs, and final validation sessions, which creates a system of iterative development where software developers and governance officials can integrate stakeholders' inputs into their respective frameworks. Co-design and co-creation are central to this project's functioning by being embedded within the 'user cases' structure.

Stakeholders are actively involved in co-design by shaping the project's methodologies and frameworks, with User Cases being structured to encourage open-ended discussions and responsivity to real time user feedback to adapt the project's design to real-world complexities. Meanwhile, co-creation was directly used in several User Cases, where stakeholders directly shaped the project's outputs in both structured and unstructured manners. By employing the technique of co-creation, the project sought to push participants produce materials and solutions that aligned with their own personal concerns about AI and big data, all the while gauging citizen perceptions and attitudes towards these technologies to better integrate appropriate responses within governance and policy structures. By using co-production, co-creation and co-design within its framework, the KT4D project attempts to further a collaborative approach where technologies are built through direct integration of citizens' inputs, supporting and promoting democratic principles along the way.

The Democratic Odyssey is a project formulated in the context of the perceived increase in instability of democratic values in the EU. Building on conclusions of the Conference on the Future of Europe, the project seeks to explore ways to merge transnational citizens' assemblies with existing participatory tools, all while ensuring the meaningful involvement and deliberation of citizens within the EU's complex democratic framework. Through this, the Democratic Odyssey's end goal is to create the foundations for a European Citizens' Assembly. This concept of the Citizens' Assembly relies on the concepts co-production, co-design and co-creation, and uses sortition to select a wide variety of European citizens to join and deliberate with regard to EU decision-making. Using a blueprint and modular framework to create a pilot assembly in Athens in September 2024, it was observed that extensive deliberation and conversating during this assembly led to consensus and common ground being formed, which in turn led to the solidifying of concrete European values and ideals. The co-design and co-creation of this vision fosters an inclusive and participatory environment, where involved citizens directly shape the direction of the Citizens' Assembly, and the institutional outcomes linked to it. The project's focus on inclusivity ensures that the design and implementation of the initiative are co-created with input from a wide array of citizens, which in turn leads to collaborative development and the creation of a feeling of shared ownership.

Sustainable PRactices of INteGration (SPRING)'s objectives were formulated in the context of the increase in influx of migrants and refugees since 2014, and in response to the need of improved integration at local, regional and nations levels across Europe. SPRING's end goal was to create a toolbox to provide integration stakeholders with the means necessary to provide effective and sustainable integration to refugees and migrants, with part of the work coming in the form of its first work package. This work package sought to engage with established and more recent communities working in the field of integration, in order to bridge the gap between academic knowledge and the practical sectors of improvement based on their integration practitioners' experiences. This was done using co-design in three phases, beginning with exploratory interviews to identify themes common to stakeholders, followed by an identification of stakeholders of problems and barriers linked to integration, and finishing with a co-designing of pathways to ideal solutions. The first two steps of this process uncovered interconnected barriers such as policy gaps, discrimination, and organisational

capacity, which in turn led to a co-design of ideal intervention pathways and scenarios. Through this, SPRING showed the value of the collaboration between integration practitioners and stakeholders by letting lived experiences guide the process of practice and policymaking. The results of the co-design within this work package fed into the project’s six other work packages, which ultimately led to the creation of a handbook on integration policy practices for newly arrived migrants and a good practice adaptation toolkit.

2 Living Lab Methodology and Techniques

In this section, we will detail the five categories central to our methodology: **Understanding, Framing, Ideating, Evaluating, and Testing**. Each of these parts of the methodology will play a crucial role in transforming the theoretical ideas into actionable strategies within the Living Labs (see Figure 1). By navigating through these phases, we will seek to gain insights into how to effectively generate creative solutions and refine concepts to ensure they are robust and impactful, as well as address any potential challenges we may encounter along the way. Each category is supported by specific techniques that will facilitate collaboration, critical thinking, and iterative development, which will ultimately lead to successful outcomes in the fifth and final stage of the methodology.

Figure 1. Living Lab methodology and associated techniques.

2.1 Understanding

This phase is the initial cornerstone of the methodology, focusing on applying critical and analytical thinking exercises to deconstruct problems and extract meaningful insights. The work undertaken during this phase aids in obtaining a deeper understanding of digital democracy and its associated concepts (governance, participation, activism, FIMI, trends, and future projections). During this phase, it is important that stakeholders obtain an equal level of knowledge and comprehension about relevant themes to allow for productive discussion around mutual understanding of the project’s central topics further on in the project. The comprehensive approach of this phase helps to avoid missteps further on in the project and

ensures that our solutions developed are well-aligned with the theoretical context associated with digital democracy. Through this thorough understanding, we lay the groundwork for effective framing, ideation, and solution development.

Techniques used

- **Journey Map¹**: maps out the user's experience with the current system or process. This technique involves creating a visual representation of the steps a user or customer goes through when interacting with a service or product using sticky notes to create a timeline of said steps. In this phase, the journey map will help identify pain points and areas for improvement by visualising the user's journey from start to finish.
- **Stakeholder Map²**: identifies and maps out all stakeholders involved in the project, categorising them by their level of influence and interest. This process will involve determining the most relevant stakeholders by charting priorities relating to potential stakeholders' power and interest on a chart relating to how high or low their power and interest in the project is. This technique ensures that all relevant perspectives are considered during the understanding phase.
- **Empathy Map³**: helps understand the user's thoughts, feelings, actions, and needs. This will involve drawing a diagram with sections for what various actors say, think, do and feel when faced with different scenarios relating to digital democracy. This helps in empathising with the user and gaining deeper insights into their experience.

2.2 Framing

This second phase helps with placing the topics and themes outlined in each work package in real-life contexts and will allow us to set clear boundaries and objectives for the development process of the project. By framing these problems effectively, we will ensure that all stakeholders have a shared understanding of the goals, constraints, and success criteria for the project. Engaging in the activities and techniques outlined below ensures that the problems we are seeking to address are well-defined and that we have a clear path forward for ideation and solution development. These elements are essential for focusing our efforts and resources on the most important and impactful areas within digital democracy.

Techniques used

- **Service Map⁴**: helps to understand the current service process, including front-stage (user-facing) and back-stage (internal) elements. This will involve a visualisation through outlining the steps an actor usually takes in the context of digital democracy on a template, the linking the front-stage and back-stage happening for each step below it. Once these have been outlined, ideas will be formulated for the various steps to identify bottlenecks and areas for improvement within the service delivery.

¹ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/journey-map>

² <https://pipdecks.com/pages/stakeholder-map>

³ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/empathy-map>

⁴ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/service-map>

- **Futures Wheel:** explores potential consequences of a trend or event by visualising its primary, secondary, and tertiary impacts. Participants will draw a circle with the central idea at the core, then brainstorm and record primary impacts in a ring around it. For each primary impact, secondary impacts will also be identified in an outer ring, and could be continued through tertiary impacts if necessary. This will help in identifying the broader implications of current issues or opportunities relating to digital democracy, providing a more visually structured way to think about the future.
- **Backcasting:** helps in framing the problem by setting clear future goals and outlining the pathways to reach them, through working backward from a desired future state to identify the steps needed to achieve it. We will begin by clearly defining the future goal, then brainstorm the milestones and actions required to reach that goal while considering potential obstacles and opportunities along the way.
- **Mind Map⁵:** useful for visually brainstorming and connecting various aspects of the problem by identifying key components, relationships and gaps, thus providing a clear and structured overview that facilitates a shared understanding among stakeholders. Participants will start with a central idea or concept, written in the centre of a page or digital canvas, then draw branches to represent main categories or subtopics. For each subtopic, participants will then add further branches to detail related ideas, thoughts, or information.

2.3 Ideating

This phase is designed to encourage stakeholders and participants from a wide variety of backgrounds to generate a multitude of ideas, which will foster creativity and innovation. This phase emphasises both the quantity and quality of ideas, allowing participants and stakeholders to explore diverse possibilities with the techniques detailed below. The most promising/original ideas and concepts provided during this phase will be refined and developed to ensure that the best ideas are carried forward for implementation in the evaluation and testing phases.

Techniques used

- **Mind Map:** helps to visually organise ideas around a central problem or opportunity. Helps in generating a wide range of ideas and exploring different pathways for potential solutions.
- **Storyboard⁶:** helps to visualise and communicate ideas as a sequence of events or interactions. Participants will start by identifying the key scenes or steps and sketch them in a series of frames or panels. Each frame will depict a moment in the narrative, including characters, actions, and dialogue. The frames will be arranged in chronological order to convey the flow of the story. This aids in developing and refining concepts by illustrating how they would work in real-world scenarios.

⁵ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/mind-map>

⁶ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/storyboard>

- **Round Robin**⁷: helps to collaboratively evolve ideas by passing them around the group, building upon the previous person's idea, leading to more robust and fully formed solutions. Each participant will contribute an initial idea or solution to a problem by writing or drawing it. Then, the idea will be passed through the group, with each participant adding to or elaborating on the previous person's contribution. This process will be continued for several rounds then observed and discussed, which allows participants to create collective input.
- **Futures Wheel**: this will stimulate creative thinking and generate new ideas about how to address future challenges or leverage opportunities of the digital democracy app.
- **Backcasting**: participants will brainstorm innovative solutions by envisioning the future of the digital democracy app then identifying the necessary steps to achieve that vision.

2.4 Evaluating

This phase ensures that only the most robust and feasible ideas and concepts are carried forward for further development and pilot testing. Through the techniques detailed below, we will critically examine each idea to aid us in making informed decisions and allowing us to focus on the ideas with the highest potential for success. This evaluation phase will help us to align our efforts with the INNOVADE's strategic objectives and our stakeholders' needs, which will lead us to a successful implementation and testing phase.

Techniques used

- **SWOT Analysis**⁸: helps evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the proposed ideas or solutions. Assists in assessing the viability and potential impact of each idea. Participants will begin by creating a grid with four quadrants, each representing one of the categories. They will list the internal strengths and weaknesses in their respective sections by focusing on factors within their control, then identify external opportunities and threats by considering a variety of factors.
- **Heart, Head, Hand**⁹: evaluates ideas based on their emotional resonance (heart), logical considerations (head), and feasibility (hand). Participants will discuss themes and ideas in detail by considering the feelings they evoke, their alignment with values and beliefs, and whether it inspires or motivates those involved (heart); then by considering data, evidence, and alignment with objectives to determine if they make sense intellectually (head); then assess the resources, capabilities, and steps required to execute them, ensuring they are realistic and achievable within given constraints. This ensures that ideas are well-rounded to address all aspects of the problem.
- **Rose, Thorn, Bud**¹⁰: evaluates ideas by identifying positive aspects (roses), challenges or drawbacks (thorns), and opportunities for improvement (buds). Participants will first

⁷ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/round-robin>

⁸ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/swot-analysis>

⁹ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/heart-head-hand>

¹⁰ <https://pipdecks.com/pages/rose-thorn-bud>

identify and list the positive aspects or strengths of the idea or situation, elements that are working well or are appreciated (roses); then they will highlight the areas that need attention or improvement (thorns); then will finally recognise potential opportunities for growth or improvement that, with further development or attention, could enhance the overall outcome or experience (buds). This refines ideas and identifies areas for further development.

- **World Café¹¹**: facilitates large group dialogue through structured conversations with alternating small groups at café-style tables over multiple rounds, which encourages participants to explore ideas and share insights in a collaborative and engaging environment. Culminates in a group harvesting session where key insights are shared and visually documented.

2.5 Testing

This final phase involves an evaluation of the prototype app in real-world scenarios to gather feedback and assess their effectiveness. The prototype will be built on the sum of all the outputs of the previous five phases, and will ensure that improvements are explored and refined based on real user interactions and performance data once it is released. This iterative approach will lead to user-centric solutions to any problems encountered through usage of the prototype, which will ensure that the app is ready for full-scale implementation.

Techniques used

- **Storyboard**: use this technique again during the testing phase to create visual representations of the prototypes. This helps in communicating the proposed changes to stakeholders and gathering feedback on their effectiveness.
- **Service Map**: update the service map to reflect the proposed changes and test how they integrate into the existing service process. This helps in identifying any potential issues or improvements before full-scale implementation.

3 Implementation of Living Labs

The objective of this section is to create a structured approach for conducting living labs that facilitate research, experimentation, and synthesis of results related to digital democracies, ultimately producing comprehensive outcome reports, useful tools and a digital democracy application.

INNOVADE's living labs methodology is developed based on the theoretical background on the co-creation concept and its key characteristics. Living Labs will be implemented through three principal phases that consider the five-phase methodology outlined in chapter 2. The following are presented in detail and have been refined following our first living lab (which is detailed in Chapter 4), where stakeholders were asked to formulate potential reflections regarding the steps in the implementation process from the point of view of citizens and public sector agencies. They were then integrated into the following steps to better consider the

¹¹ <https://theworldcafe.com/key-concepts-resources/world-cafe-method/>

various stakeholders and participants that will partake in these living labs, providing a more comprehensive and reliable structure for implementation.

Phase	I - Planning and Preparation	II - Living Lab Implementation	III - Analysis and Reporting
Time	LL-6 months	LL-2 weeks	LL+2 months
	Define Objectives and Scope <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establish clear goals for the LL; Determine the specific aspects of digital democracies to be addressed. 	Participant Involvement and Engagement <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct workshops, focus groups, and surveys to gather input from users; Involve users in the co-creation of solutions through collaborative design sessions. 	Analysis of results <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate findings from different aspects of the project to form a comprehensive understanding; Use of visual aids (charts, graphs, infographics).
	Identify Stakeholders and Partners <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identify and engage key stakeholders; Form a steering committee to oversee the living lab process. 	Comprehensive Data Collection <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use surveys, interviews, observation, and digital analytics to collect data during testing phases; Data collection from the participants; Ensure data collection methods are ethical and comply with relevant regulations. 	Outcome Reporting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Write detailed report presenting the results.
	Scenario Development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop real-life scenarios and use cases to test different aspects of digital democracies; Ensure scenarios reflect diverse user experiences and needs. 		Recommendations and way forward <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop actionable recommendations based on the findings Inputs for improving the output/product
	Develop a Detailed Project Plan <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create a timeline with milestones and deliverables; Define roles and responsibilities for all participants; Logistical planning considerations (funding, technology, expertise). 		

Table 1. Timeline matrix of the Living Lab implementation process

3.1 Planning and Preparation

3.1.1 Define Objectives and Scope

- Establish clear goals for the living lab:** Living Labs are designed for creating multidisciplinary and multistakeholder knowledge. This is why clear objectives need to be defined for each living lab by the organiser. As an example, a living lab can be organised for improving citizen engagement, enhancing transparency, or testing new voting technologies. Vague objectives can cause difficulty in understanding and

properly implementing the Living Lab and receiving the contributions to the Living Lab. It is crucial to consider the added value for different stakeholders involved in the project. From the **public sector's point of view**, there needs to be an understanding of the benefits of adopting the new tools coming from the Living Labs when they already have existing systems in place. There needs to be a robust outline of the ways by which the Living Labs' outputs complement or improve existing systems to encourage engagement or adoption of new tools by the public sector. From a **citizen's point of view**, there is a need to clarify what they get out of their involvement in the Living Labs and how their contributions lead to meaningful change, particularly how it enhances their daily lives and empowers them within the digital democracy landscape.

- **Determine the specific aspects of digital democracies to be addressed:** Each Living Lab is designed for specific aspects of digital democracies. A well-defined scope is significant to receive proper and useful contributions in a structured way. The scope of the Living Labs will be defined in line with the following phases of a problem-solving process: understanding, framing, ideating, evaluating, and test. By focusing on these five phases, our Living Labs can ensure that they address real-world challenges systematically, fostering innovation and co-creation among stakeholders. This structured approach not only enhances the relevance of the contributions but also facilitates the implementation of solutions that are both practical and impactful.

3.1.2 Identify Stakeholders and Partners

- **Identify and engage key stakeholders:** proper recruitment and engagement of relevant stakeholders ensures that diverse perspectives are included and that the subsequent Living Lab outputs are more representative overall. This representative stakeholder base will include citizens, government agencies, NGOs, academia, and private sector partners. Additionally, there should also be an incorporation of multidisciplinary teams of academics, governance representatives, experts and community leaders, civil society organisations (CSOs), and students. It is important to understand that certain socioeconomic groups are more difficult to reach than others (due to accessibility concerns, scepticism about participation, and logistical barriers such as transportation, timing, and physical access), which could hinder stakeholder representation within the Living Labs. Clear communication, transparent outreach, and trust-building measures can help mitigate fears of scams or exclusion. A waiting list system can also help regulate participation and ensure a balanced, diverse group that reflects different backgrounds and experiences. Additionally, we will deploy methods to guarantee a balanced outtake of stakeholders per living lab, with a representative distribution of stakeholders relevant to each living lab.
- **Form a steering committee to oversee the living lab process:** this committee will include representatives from key stakeholder groups as highlighted above, who can provide guidance, monitor progress, and appropriately address challenges will they arise. Additionally, it is important to identify and recruit individuals who are both willing and proficient in moderation to facilitate discussions during Living Labs (a preparatory session will be conducted to familiarise them with the Living Lab process and ensure alignment with its objectives). The steering committee will consider which strategies

can best ensure inclusivity and address potential language barriers/gaps. Particular attention will also be given to the location and timing of the Living Labs to ensure that it is accessible in terms of both time and location to ensure maximum attendance and representation.

3.1.3 Scenario Development

- **Develop real-life scenarios and use cases to test different aspects of digital democracies:** the simulation of real-world challenges will enable stakeholders to assess how proposed solutions function in different governance contexts. Through presenting various scenarios to stakeholders involving concepts such as e-participation, digital activism, and FIMI, the results of their deliberation can provide valuable insights into the impact of digital democracy. Various workshop techniques, outlined in more detail in Chapters 2 and 4, will provide the necessary input to formulate these scenarios.
- **Ensure scenarios reflect diverse user experiences and needs:** this includes considering variations in levels of the stakeholders' digital literacy, socioeconomic status, language proficiency, accessibility requirements, and levels of civic engagement. Considering these factors within the development of scenarios allows for more adaptable and relevant solutions for a broader spectrum of society, instead of benefiting certain specific demographics. We will visualise the entire service process, including frontstage (user-facing) and back-stage (internal) elements. This will help ensure that scenarios consider the full range of user experiences and system interactions.

3.1.4 Develop a Detailed Project Plan

- **Create a timeline with milestones and deliverables:** the timeline will provide stakeholders with a clear outline of their expected/required time investment, including when activities will take place, how they will be organised, and what is expected of stakeholders at each stage of the project. Informative and accessible materials will be prepared to ensure all participants, regardless of background, can easily understand the project's schedule and objectives. This material will be shared in a timely manner to allow stakeholders ample time to prepare themselves in anticipation of the Living Labs. Additionally, the timeline will be designed with a consideration of both efficiency and flexibility, to allow for potential adjustments all while maintaining accountability and transparency. Lastly, it is important to allocate appropriate and significant time between Living Labs to better iterate findings into INNOVADE's research, and outputs going forward.
- **Define roles and responsibilities for all participants:** providing explicit guidance to stakeholders on these expectations and channels for involvement enhances clarity and reinforces the legitimacy of the Living Lab. Stakeholders need to know and understand how their inputs will be incorporated into the Living Lab process to foster their trust and sustained engagement within the project.
- **Logistical planning considerations (funding, technology, expertise):** these will support the operational needs of the Living Lab, including financial allocations for

travel reimbursements, venue bookings, catering, and potential participation incentives should the need arise. Access to the appropriate technological infrastructure and expert support is critical for the seamless execution of activities; this access needs to be confirmed as early as possible to ensure this seamlessness. From the **public service's point of view**, there needs to be a consideration of maintenance costs and other recurring expenses that must be integrated into annual budgets to ensure sustainability. Communication regarding available resources and their allocation needs to be as transparent as possible to foster the trust of the stakeholders and encourage continued engagement from them.

3.2 Living Lab Implementation

3.2.1 Participant Involvement and Engagement

- **Conduct workshops, focus groups, and surveys to gather input from users:** this will involve collecting diverse perspectives and ensuring that solutions align the project's outputs with stakeholder needs. Participants will be contacted in advance, and preliminary testing and evaluation of these input gathering methods will be conducted first, with results shared with stakeholders transparently (public service stakeholders require evidence of prior testing and measurable outcomes to assess the viability of proposed solutions).
- **Involve users in the co-creation of solutions through collaborative design sessions:** engaging users in the co-creation process ensures that solutions are both relevant and user-centred, as these sessions provide an environment where participants can share their insights, experiences and expectations to better formulate outputs that address the daily challenges they face. These sessions will integrate diverse perspectives to encourage open dialogue, creative problem-solving, and iterative feedback loops to shape outputs in a robust manner. Participants may require support to engage meaningfully (particularly if they lack confidence in their ability to contribute), so providing clear guidance through preparatory materials such as informational cards and leaflets, demonstrations and presentations with clear communication, and structured facilitation by moderators can help participants feel more comfortable and empowered. Group dynamics are important to consider in this regard, so we must be wary of them and make effort to make participants feel present and included, so that they feel comfortable in sharing their inputs instead of keeping their experiences to themselves due to unbalanced group dynamics. We will identify points and opportunities by mapping the steps users take in their interaction with digital democracy tools during these sessions.

3.2.2 Comprehensive Data Collection

- **Use surveys, interviews, observation, and digital analytics to collect data during testing phases:** by employing these methods, a well-rounded understanding of user experiences and challenges can be obtained. Surveys and interviews will provide valuable qualitative insights into user perceptions and satisfaction, while observational studies help identify usability barriers in real-world settings. Digital analytics will offer quantitative data to reveal trends and areas for improvement. One such technique,

should it be technically feasible, would be to use eye tracking to consider user's attention when using the app and acting accordingly to improve the performance of the app. A combination of these approaches will ensure that stakeholders have a robust evidence base to refine the app before full-scale deployment.

- **Data collection from the participants:** quantitative data, such as app usage metrics, participation rates, and survey responses, will provide measurable indicators of success, while qualitative insights from interviews, focus groups, and open-ended feedback will capture users' experiences and expectations. By analysing both types of data, we will identify strengths and areas for improvement to implement into the final outputs of the project. From **a public service perspective**, it is important to factor in that staff may require training to effectively integrate new tools into their workflows.
- **Ensure data collection methods are ethical and comply with relevant regulations:** data collection must adhere to strict ethical guidelines and comply with relevant legal frameworks, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the AI Act. Public services and project stakeholders will need to ensure that personal data is handled securely, with adequate protection against cyber-attacks. Ensuring transparency in data usage policies, storage, and processing methods is critical for maintaining trust among participants. We will also need to obtain explicit consent for the use of photos and videos in reports, promotional materials, or public communications to safeguarding participants' rights.

3.3 Analysis and Reporting

3.3.1 Analysis of Results

- **Integrate findings from different aspects of the project to form a comprehensive understanding:** this will entail a compiling of various insights and data from the other work packages of the project to create a holistic view of the outcomes and implications of digital democracy. This compiling of data will be applied to the results of the living labs to complement it and provide a fuller overview and analysis of the results.
- **Use of visual aids (charts, graphs, infographics):** these will highlight key findings, patterns, and correlations, making the data more accessible and impactful for readers. We will ensure that the visuals are accompanied by clear explanations to provide context and enhance comprehension. These visual aids will comprise of charts to illustrate quantitative data trends, graphs to show comparisons over time or across different groups, and infographics to present complex information in an easily digestible format.

3.3.2 Outcome Reporting

- **Write detailed report presenting the results:** This will be a comprehensive report that documents each Living Lab, including their setup, specific materials used, participant demographics, and final findings. The report will be structured to include sections on methodology, findings, discussion, and conclusions. It will include a detailed account of activities conducted, participant engagement levels, and anonymised feedback collected. Key results will be presented with both qualitative and quantitative data, and we will discuss their alignment with initial objectives. We will

assess the impact on participants and stakeholders and provide recommendations for future iterations. Each LL report will be added to this document as new chapters.

3.3.3 Recommendations and Way Forward

- **Develop actionable recommendations based on the findings.** After each LL, action items will be defined to feed other tasks and work packages of the project.
- **Inputs for improving the output/product.** Inputs will be defined by partners to improve the methodology and also to improve the planned tools and outputs of the project.

4 INNOVADE Living Labs

INNOVADE will create multidisciplinary and multistakeholder knowledge and expertise bases on shaping its deliverables to increase civic participation through digital democracy in the form of Living Labs. The Living Labs will be workshops where multiple stakeholders participate, such as multidisciplinary teams of academics, officials / representatives of governance structures, citizens, civil society organisations, and support networks. The Living Labs will function as an inclusive and participatory platform for cooperation, inquiry, exchange, communication and co-creation. The expertise of the Living Labs will be leveraged *ad hoc* at different stages and will be key to validate the evidence-based approach to develop project deliverables. The timing for the organisation of the Living Labs will indicate critical junctions where the inputs received during them will inform development processes (see *Figure 2*).

The “Living Labs” are at the heart of the INNOVADE value proposition, and therefore, rather than risking that they might become disconnected from the heart of the project’s research and development, the tasks to optimally deliver these key exploitation points are distributed throughout the WPs. INNOVADE organises seven living labs throughout the project.

Figure 2. INNOVADE Living Labs timeline.

4.1 LL1: Defining the LL Methodology

Objective: The living lab methodology is to be determined in LL1, aiming to ensure coordination between the partners towards a coherent and shared approach across the Living Labs, and across the three years of the project. It compiles a project level glossary of agreed terms of reference for the purposes of our collaborative.

Responsibilities: Led by BtH, contributed by all partners.

Participants: All INNOVADE partners.

Phase: 1 – Understand.

Techniques: The Journey Map technique was used to understand the challenges of different stakeholders for implementing Living Labs in different steps from planning to reporting. The participants were split into two groups (one making a digital Journey Map, one making a analogue Journey Map) and assigned with roles as citizens and government institutions. They were tasked with highlighting concerns from the point of view of both of these stakeholders to consider within the elaboration of the methodology. Please see the following figures for the implementation of LL1.

Result: INNOVADE Living Lab methodology is defined including phases, techniques and implementation guidelines. Challenges highlighted by partners during the living lab were considered and directly implemented to formulate this methodology in part based on their thoughts and concerns.

Figure 3. LL1 group working on the physical journey map.

Figure 4. LL1 group working on the digital journey map.

Figure 5. LL1 Paperboard journey map.

Figure 6. LL1 Digital journey map.

4.2 LL2: Envisioning Digital Democracy Based on Research and Best Practices

Objective: To collaboratively envision an optimum digital democracy by leveraging state-of-the-art literature, future development predictions, and best practices. Participants will discuss the first draft of the D2.1 Interdisciplinary Knowledge Base on Digital Democracy (KER 1), focusing on applying Mind Maps and Futures Wheel to align with the content of deliverable D2.1.

Responsibilities: Led by BtH, organised by UPB, contributed by all partners.

Participants: All INNOVADE partners, external stakeholders and experts.

Phase: 2 – Frame

Techniques: participants will use Mind Maps to envision an ideal digital democracy. Digital Democracy will be the central aspect, with key categories from deliverable D1.2 organised around it: deliberative democracy, online participation, open governance, digital activism, and e-voting. Groups will each create a mind map for one of these dimensions, identifying ideal-type features and desirable aspects. Each group will present and compare their results, with one poster per dimension. For each of the five aspects of digital democracy, a small group will conduct a Futures Wheel. The inner category will be the ideal-type digital democracy aspect

identified with Mind Maps. Groups will identify potential direct and indirect impacts on society, using the content of chapters 7 and 8 from D2.1 to inform the discussion.

Result: A refined draft/annex of the D2.1 Interdisciplinary Knowledge Base on Digital Democracy (KER 1), incorporating insights from Mind Maps and Futures Wheel exercises; a separate document detailing the outcomes of the techniques applied during the workshop.

4.3 LL3: Matching Citizen and Government Expectations from Digitalisation

Objective: To explore and enhance communication and action between citizens and government agencies regarding digital democracy by evaluating advantages, disadvantages, and improvement methods.

Responsibilities: Led by BtH, DFKI to provide a design, human-in-the-loop UX/UI perspective. Contributed by KUL, DFKI, SG, SVG.

Participants: Defined partners, CSOs and Government Agencies

Phase: 3 – Ideate.

Techniques: A Mind Map will help visually organise ideas around the central theme of improving citizen-government interactions, generating a wide range of potential solutions and exploring various pathways. Storyboarding will assist in visualising and communicating these ideas as sequences of events, illustrating how proposed solutions might function in real-world scenarios and aiding in their development and refinement. The Round Robin technique will be used to facilitate collaborative idea evolution by having participants build upon each other's concepts, leading to more robust and comprehensive solutions. A Futures Wheel will be developed to stimulate creative thinking by exploring potential consequences of trends in digital democracy, helping to anticipate future challenges and opportunities. Lastly, Backcasting will be used to enable participants to envision a desired future state for digital democracy and work backward to identify the potential steps and actions to achieve that vision, ensuring a strategic and innovative approach to enhancing communication and action through digital platforms.

Result: Insights and recommendations based on the review of Task 4.2 and Task 4.3 results.

4.4 LL4: Balancing Between Citizen, Government Preferences and Technical Possibilities

Objective: To review prior findings and generate a draft specification for the Digital Democracy App by engaging citizens and government agencies in a collaborative Living Lab.

Responsibilities: Led by BtH, contributors: KUL, DFKI, HC, SG, SVG, CIB. DFKI will provide multiple UX/UI examples to assess user preferences for interacting with the potential app.

Participants: Defined partners, CSOs, citizens and government agencies.

Phase: 4 – Evaluate.

Techniques: A SWOT Analysis will help evaluate the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with the proposed app, providing a comprehensive assessment of its viability and potential impact. The Heart, Head, Hand technique will be used to ensure that the app's design and features resonate with users, as they are logical/feasible to implement while addressing all aspects of user needs and technical considerations. The Rose, Thorn, Bud technique will further refine the app's concept by identifying positive aspects, challenges, and opportunities for improvement, guiding iterative development. The World Café technique will help in facilitating large group dialogues through structured, small-group conversations over multiple rounds, encouraging participants to explore ideas and share insights collaboratively, which will end in a group harvesting session where key insights are documented, fostering a rich exchange of perspectives and contributing to a well-rounded and user-centric app specification.

Result: A draft specification for the Digital Democracy App, informed by prior findings and consensus among participants; insights into user preferences for app interactions, based on UX/UI assessments.

4.5 LL5: Envisioning Future Digital Democracy Based on Social and Technological Trends

Objective: To discuss and detail pathways to achieve an optimum digital democracy by analysing the ecosystem required to uphold a flourishing digital democracy.

Responsibilities: Led by BtH, contributors: UPB, KUL, ICTLC, HC. Partners will present research results, engage in discussions, participate in red teaming, and synthesise discussion points.

Participants: Partners and experts.

Phase: 3 - Ideate and 4 – Evaluate.

Techniques: A Futures Wheel can be developed to allow partners to explore potential consequences of current trends or events, visualising primary, secondary, and tertiary impacts to anticipate future challenges and opportunities in digital democracy. Meanwhile, Backcasting can be used to enable the group to set clear future goals for digital democracy and outline the necessary steps to achieve them by working backward from a desired future state, creating a strategic roadmap for realising this vision.

Result: A holistic and multi-perspective understanding of pathways to achieve an optimum digital democracy; synthesised discussion points and considerations to inform recommendations in Deliverables 3.2 and 3.3; enhanced insights into the ecosystem required for a flourishing digital democracy.

4.6 LL6 - LL7: Application Litmus Test with Citizens of Different Digital Literacy Skills

Objective: To test the pedagogical design of the app.

Responsibilities: Led by BtH, contributors: CIB, SG, SMV.

Participants: Citizens, CSOs.

Phase: 5 – Test.

Techniques: The Storyboard technique can be employed during the testing phase to create visual representations of the app's prototypes. This involves developing a sequence of illustrations that depict the user journey and key interactions within the app. This visual mapping will allow stakeholders to better understand the intended improvements and provide feedback on their effectiveness. This will ensure that all stakeholders are aligned on the design goals and can contribute meaningful insights to refine the pedagogical aspects of the app. The Service Map can be updated to reflect the proposed changes and test how they integrate into the existing service process. This will involve creating a detailed diagram that outlines the steps users take when interacting with the app, highlighting touchpoints, actions, and user experiences. The mapping out of the service process will highlight potential issues or areas for improvement before the app's final implementation.

Result: Evaluation and feedback on the pedagogical design of the app.

Conclusion

This chapter shall include a summary of key conclusions, next steps (e.g., update of document during the project or input to other tasks/deliverables), and exploitation view for future use.

This document constructs a robust framework for INNOVADE Living Labs to follow. Beginning with a theoretical framework, which distinguished between co-design, co-production and co-creation, the latter has been selected as the most appropriate concept to apply to INNOVADE living labs. Building on this, the principal characteristics of co-creation are established alongside its potential challenges and resolutions. This led us to a definition of living labs along with its key characteristics and requirements, which was then illustrated through three examples of co-creation in action (KT4D, Democratic Odyssey and SPRING).

Based on the theoretical background including real examples, this chapter defines INNOVADE Living Labs methodology including associated co-creation techniques for each step. Divided into 5 steps (Understand, Frame, Ideate Evaluate, and Test), this methodology is structured to generate robust and specific results by a variety of stakeholders through creative techniques selected to create an iterative process, which ultimately leads to the successful implementation of the living labs and successive development of the digital democracy app.

After detailing these five phases, this document delves into further detail on the implementation of the living labs. Implementation is structured into four phases, namely (1) planning and preparation, (2) user-centric design and co-creation, (3) iterative implementation, and (4) analysis and reporting. These were initially drafted before our first Living Lab, then were refined following it to factors inputs from project stakeholders to better consider potential citizen and public sector points of view. This detailed explanation of the implementation ensures their proper organisation and creates a uniform and streamlined approach to their design.

Finally, the document focuses on the implementation of upcoming Living Labs (LL2 to LL7), defines objectives, phase, responsibilities, participants and potential techniques of each Living Lab. By following this structured methodology, INNOVADE living labs can effectively explore and enhance various aspects of digital democracies and INNOVADE outputs and results.

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Annex

Living Lab Project Checklist for Stakeholders

N°	Task	Result
Phase 1 – Planning and Preparation		
A	Define Objectives and Scope	
1	Establish clear goals for the Living Lab.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Determine specific aspects of digital democracies to be addressed.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Consider added value for different stakeholders.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Outline how Living Lab outputs complement existing systems.	<input type="checkbox"/>
B	Identify Stakeholders and Partners	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Identify and engage key stakeholders (citizens, government agencies, NGOs, academia, private sector).	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Incorporate multidisciplinary teams (academics, governance representatives, experts, community leaders, CSOs, students).	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Implement clear communication and transparent outreach.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Form a steering committee to oversee the Living Lab process.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Identify and recruit proficient moderators for discussions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Consider strategies for inclusivity and address potential language barriers.	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Ensure accessibility in terms of location and timing.	<input type="checkbox"/>
C	Scenario Development	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Develop real-life scenarios and use cases to test aspects of digital democracies.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Ensure scenarios reflect diverse user experiences and needs.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Consider variations in digital literacy, socioeconomic status, language proficiency, accessibility requirements, and civic engagement.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Visualise the entire service process, including frontstage and backstage elements.	<input type="checkbox"/>
D	Develop a Detailed Project Plan	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Create a timeline with milestones and deliverables.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Define roles and responsibilities for all participants.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Plan logistics (funding, technology, expertise).	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Ensure financial allocations for travel reimbursements, venue bookings, catering, and participation incentives.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Confirm access to technological infrastructure and expert support.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Consider maintenance costs and recurring expenses for sustainability.	<input type="checkbox"/>
7	Maintain transparency in communication regarding available resources.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phase 2 – Living Lab Implementation		
A	Participant Involvement and Engagement	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Conduct workshops, focus groups, and surveys to gather input from users.	<input type="checkbox"/>

2	Involve users in co-creation of solutions through collaborative design sessions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Provide clear guidance and preparatory materials to support meaningful engagement.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Ensure balanced group dynamics and inclusivity during sessions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Map user interactions with digital democracy tools.	<input type="checkbox"/>
B	Comprehensive Data Collection	<input type="checkbox"/>
1	Use surveys, interviews, observation, and digital analytics to collect data.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Gather quantitative data (app usage metrics, participation rates, survey responses).	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Collect qualitative insights from interviews, focus groups, and open-ended feedback.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Ensure data collection methods are ethical and comply with relevant regulations (GDPR, AI Act).	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Obtain explicit consent for the use of photos and videos.	<input type="checkbox"/>
Phase 3 – Analysis and Reporting		
A	Analysis of Results	
1	Integrate findings from different aspects of the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Use visual aids (charts, graphs, infographics) to highlight key findings.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Provide clear explanations to accompany visuals.	<input type="checkbox"/>
B	Outcome Reporting	
1	Write a detailed report presenting the results.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Document each Living Lab, including setup, materials used, participant demographics, and findings.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Include sections on methodology, findings, discussion, and conclusions.	<input type="checkbox"/>
4	Present key results with both qualitative and quantitative data.	<input type="checkbox"/>
5	Assess impact on participants and stakeholders.	<input type="checkbox"/>
6	Provide recommendations for future iterations.	<input type="checkbox"/>
C	Recommendations and Way Forward	
1	Develop actionable recommendations based on the findings.	<input type="checkbox"/>
2	Define action items to feed other tasks and work packages of the project.	<input type="checkbox"/>
3	Improve methodology and planned tools and outputs based on partner inputs	<input type="checkbox"/>

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